

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

WAYS TO FURTHER REGULATE THE PROCESS OF ECONOMIC RECOVERY IN UKRAINE IN THE POST-WAR PERIOD

Lenets V.

Entrepreneur,

PhD student of the Department of Public Administration and Land Management

Classical Private University,

DykankaMlyn Limited Liability Company

Poltava.

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Abstract

The article reveals ways to further regulate the process of economic recovery in Ukraine in the post-war period. The article examines the process of planning the post-war restoration and development of Ukraine, its methodological foundations and specifics. Attention is focused on the importance of using elements of global experience (including the Marshall Plan), ensuring food security of Ukraine in accordance with the historical experience of the post-war restoration of French agriculture, taking into account the role of large-scale business in the post-war restoration and technical modernization of the country's production, the need to include in the plans for the restoration the state policy of import substitution and export promotion in the system of post-war restoration measures.

Planning is an important first step for the reconstruction of Ukraine after the war and the implementation of its strategic goals, subject to the use of global experience of restoring post-war economies, with its creative development and adaptation to Ukrainian realities.

Keywords: planning, state authorities, economic recovery of Ukraine, modernization of production, food security, import substitution, export promotion.

Introduction. The process of planning for the post-war reconstruction and development of Ukraine actually began in the first months of Russia's large-scale aggression. It should include both covering material damage caused by the war, as well as restoring destroyed infrastructure capacities and structural modernization of the Ukrainian economy, as well as the return and re-adaptation of both participants in the Russian-Ukrainian war (combatants) and internally displaced persons (IDPs) who are now located outside the country [3].

The planning process itself is already an element of state regulation of the process of economic recovery in Ukraine in the post-war period since it includes such aspects as defining goals, choosing strategies and determining actions required to achieve these goals within the limited (in our case) resources available to the organization. Planning is one of the main functions of administrative management, which enables the state to determine the direction of development and ways to achieve success in the long term.

Goal of the article. To investigate ways to further regulate the process of economic recovery in Ukraine in the post-war period and the role of planning in this process.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The problems of studying the ways of further regulation of the process of economic recovery of Ukraine in the post-war period and the use of foreign experience of post-war reconstruction of the country, the development and transformation of its economy as a modern state, and the paradigm of "post-war economic modernization of the state" are now quite vividly discussed in

foreign and domestic scientific, practical and socio-political discourse. Over the last two years alone, dozens of publications related to public administration and economics, political science and sociology, legal science and communication studies have joined this discourse field. Nevertheless, the topic remains relevant and understudied, given the constant tense dynamics of geopolitical changes during the Russian-Ukrainian war.

Research methodology. Planning of state and local government bodies (*especially large millionaire cities*) includes the development of strategic and operational plans [2].

The strategic plan defines the long-term goals of the state for the recovery of its economy and ways to achieve them, while the operational plan defines specific step-by-step steps (short-term in the time interval of program implementation) required to achieve these goals in the near future of the country.

Planning also includes determining the appropriate budget (*or finding the required finances*), resources, and distributing them between different projects and tasks. State planning helps the current authorities (central authorities, in particular) to make informed decisions, focus on the projected prospects for future development, and improve the coordination of actions of contractors within the country and investors outside to achieve the goal [6].

The planning process involves predicting future events in the state. This helps to reduce uncertainty in its development caused by political and geopolitical factors, changes in technology and the conjuncture of a globalized global market, etc. Plans can provide for sufficient conditions to eliminate these uncertainties or

measures to reduce their negative impact on development.

In planning, management control involves maintaining the right direction of activity by limiting deviations from plans or standards. It is during the planning process that management sets standards for work. They are benchmarks for evaluating actual performance. In other words, planning and control are similar to the inseparable twins of management, including controlling planning objects [6].

An important role is played by the search for alternative plans or actions in the implementation of specific and important projects. Without resorting to the search for alternative approaches to solving problematic issues, government officials are likely to be guided by their limited imagination in a certain way. To prevent this from happening, it is essential to contact scientific, research, and public structures for information that will provide information and suggestions, and be aware of foreign experience on this issue. As a rule, there are always several alternative ways to solve any problem. The manager should be able to find, know them, and filter out the most untenable alternatives in order to get a small number of alternatives for the final choice in making a decision, while reducing the risks of making wrong decisions.

For operational planning, which takes place at a lower level, as it revolves around the basic details of how any particular goal or task can be achieved using available resources, the level of managerial governance in regional and local authorities is important. It is usually performed to find the right marketing plans, the most appropriate production methods, various organizational tools and actions for executing project processes [6].

Tactical planning usually takes place at the regional level. Tactical planning is responsible for the planning from which the mission can be achieved at the regional level of the state, as follows from their specification [2]. At the planning level, decisions are made related to the services or products that need to be added, as well as pricing, equipment, systems, amount of capital investment, etc.

Presentation of the main material. Strategic planning takes place at the top management level, where senior management tries to achieve long-term goals using the resources available at the moment or in the future. Strategic revolves around defining the mission of the state (government), clarifying all financial requirements, allocating resources, ensuring power relations in the organization, etc. While planning is crucial to achieving more favorable outcomes, it also includes some internal and hidden limitations.

It is expedient to consider certain features of the processes of strategic and operational planning in the recovery of the Ukrainian economy in the post-war period, which should be included in the plan for the restoration of Ukraine from the point of view of leading scientists.

The country's economic recovery plans that have been implemented in Finland, Japan, Vietnam, Korea, Bosnia, Herzegovina, Germany, Rwanda, the United

Kingdom and other countries cannot be fully scrupulously implemented in detail as a plan for the restoration of Ukraine, and only its individual provisions or fragments are possible. For Ukraine, the very essence of planning the process of restoring the country's economic complex, its education and culture is of vital importance.

We have noted that in the process of planning the country's reconstruction, the government should receive information advice from its scientific, analytical, and research institutions. The National Institute for Strategic Studies has a strong say here. The Deputy Director of the National Institute for Strategic Studies Doctor of Economics, Senior Researcher Ya. Zhalilo investigating the Marshall Plan for Ukraine has identified false historical analogies and real needs of Ukraine [1, p. 27]. He notes that the practice of identifying the government's draft national plan for the restoration of Ukraine with the historical Marshall Plan as the basis for the restoration of Western Europe after the Second World War has become widespread in Ukraine, which is incorrect.

At the same time, in his opinion, the idealization of the influence of the Marshall Plan (MP 2.0) is often combined with a superficial understanding of its essence. Drawing historical analogies of the European Marshall Plan with the situation in Ukraine, it is important to realize that the key task of the Marshall Plan 2.0 for post-war Ukraine should be to form an economic basis for accelerated European integration. Therefore, MP 2.0 may be narrower in terms of content, scope and prospects for direct funding, but it should focus on the multi-level rapid reintegration of Ukraine and its subjects into pan-European processes, support and promote reforms essential for the implementation of the tasks of candidates and dynamic acquisition of EU membership.

Therefore, MP 2.0 for Ukraine, as noted by Ya. Zhalilo, should include the following processes:

- "to articulate the mutually beneficial implementation of the Plan for Ukraine and European partners – that is, to cover not only Ukraine, but also the EU countries;
- to guarantee the formation of a stable predictable space and effective partners for the work of European partners in the Ukrainian market, their participation in the implementation of restoration projects;
- to provide for the formation of high-quality financial mechanisms for channeling the resources of international financial assistance to Ukraine for recovery through the budget and banking systems;
- to formulate a vision of Ukraine's promising place in the European Union (EU), including solving global problems – multi-vector security (including food), demography, climate change, the digital revolution, etc.;
- to determine ways to implement all types of common European policy in Ukraine, in particular, agricultural, competitive, regional, transport, environmental, energy, etc.;
- to determine the directions of industrial (agricultural) cooperation within the framework of the restoration goals;

- to determine the directions of strengthening logistics ties between Ukraine and the EU;
- to establish directions of technical assistance to state and local government bodies in the implementation of European practices” and experience [4. p. 28].

The scientist-economist T. Bodnarchuk, from the Economic History Unit of the Institute of Economics and Forecasting of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine State-owned University, emphasizes the need to include in the plans for the restoration of Ukraine the policy of import substitution and export promotion in the system of measures for the post-war recovery of the economy and economy of the country as a whole. This is the post-war experience of Western European countries, which should be used in planning restoration and modernization in Ukraine [1. c. 41].

“Further European integration and active trade and economic cooperation should become a determinant of the post-war economic recovery of Ukraine, but today there are risks of increasing the country’s import dependence and losing its competitive positions in international markets. This actualizes the issue of developing an effective trade and economic policy that would contribute to the protection of national interests and structural transformation of the domestic economic system, which, in turn, determines the importance of studying the historical practice of state regulation of export-import activities. From this point of view, the experience of Western European countries is of particular value.

In the post-war years, the foreign trade policy of Western European countries was aimed at restricting imports and strengthening national exports, which provided for the application of customs-tariff, financial, tax, and administrative measures. In particular, high rates of customs tariffs on imports of certain groups of finished products were maintained, domestic taxation for foreign producers was tightened, and export was supported through export lending and subsidies. In order to stimulate exports, European currencies were devalued, which also prevented the outflow of gold abroad, eased the burden of external debt and created favorable conditions for the inflow of direct investment.

The development of exports required direct government support for national production, which was carried out *through the nationalization of certain industries*, the establishment of public-private partnerships, production subsidies, preferential taxation, direct financing and foreign investment. Levers of state economic influence and enormous financial support within the framework of the Marshall Plan were aimed at the development of strategic industries of industrial production – mechanical engineering, automotive, chemical and pharmaceutical industries, energy, radio and electrical industries, etc., which eventually became the basis for the intensification of technological exports, diversification of vectors of commodity flows, creation of favorable conditions for trade and economic integration of the countries of the Western European region. Taking into account the experience of Western European countries, the main priorities of Ukraine’s eco-

nomical development in the post-war period are the restoration and promotion of strategic production sectors on an innovative basis” [1, p. 41].

To ensure Ukraine’s food security, it is important to take advantage of the historical experience of the post-war restoration of French agriculture. The scientist L. Didkovska actualizes the historical and economic assessment of the process of restoring French agriculture after World War II to extrapolate this experience during the post-war revival of the agricultural sector of the Ukrainian economy.

The agrarian reform in France after the Second World War ensured the elimination of the inefficient system of large-scale land ownership in agriculture, the redistribution of land ownership in favor of small producers, the social development of rural areas and the strengthening of food security. The model of development of family-type farming was chosen as the basis of the country’s agricultural structure.

The French National Institute of Agricultural Research has stimulated the transition from traditional forms of management to market-based business farms, scientifically justified ways to increase agricultural yields, prospects for the production and use of agricultural machinery. Thanks to SAFER’s efforts, the market turnover of agricultural land has become tightly regulated, focused on protecting the national agricultural producer. The success of the policy of forming a stable private capital market in French agriculture was ensured by innovations in the lease of agricultural land (1946), encouraging farmers by regulating the land market to expand farms, combining farmers into cooperatives, a high level of budget support for farmers, stimulating capital investment through subsidies, and forming an organized agricultural market at the pan-European level.

To solve the problems of the agricultural sector, a transparent procurement and sales infrastructure has been created based on cooperation and integration with trade, food and processing industry enterprises. Thanks to a purposeful and consistent policy in the agricultural sector, France not only ensured the food security of its own country in the few post-war years, but also became a global exporter of agricultural products. The concept of agrarian transformation was legalized in the Law On Agrarian Policy (1960), which contributed to increasing agricultural productivity; introduction of technical innovations in agricultural production; development of markets for agricultural products; preservation of undeveloped land; support for family farms and rural development; ensuring social protection of farmers and persons employed in agriculture; regional development of agriculture, taking into account the specifics of the area. Of particular interest in the process of post-war restoration of agriculture in Ukraine is the French experience of forming a stable private capital market in agriculture; state support for cooperatives; redistribution of land between different forms of management, taking into account national interests and priorities, etc. [1, p. 42].

It is impossible to underestimate the role of large-scale business in the post-war restoration and technical modernization of Ukrainian production. It is worth us-

ing the experience of post-war Germany. The researcher T. Slyvka states that after the end of World War II, large industrial concerns became the technological basis of the German “economic miracle”. The rapid and successful post-war resumption of production in the concerns is due to a number of factors successfully combined, in particular:

- A significant part of industrial facilities and equipment remained intact after the bombing and could start working as soon as possible. Industrial equipment was relatively new: in 1945, the service life of 34% of industrial equipment was five years.

- Already in the late 1940s and early 1950s, patents exported in particular to the United States were returned, and control over research was relaxed and restrictions on technological development were lifted.

- Successful management of the corporate sector was able to successfully reorient itself to new markets in the United States and

- Extensive use of advanced pre-war and wartime technology when entering new markets and, as a result, strong positions in negotiations in the process of concluding agreements on joint activities with American and British companies (for example, German *BASF* and American *Shell*, German *Bayer* and UK *British Petroleum*).

- West German companies gradually invested Revenues from domestic sales and export supplies in new technology. Volkswagen, for example, only after successful sales at home and abroad in the late 1940s and early 1950s, using pre-war and military factories and technology, began to invest significant resources in new factory and technical improvements. The innovations implemented at Volkswagen before were mainly organizational.

- American and British companies were extremely interested in technological cooperation with German industrial giants.

Thus, as the historical experience of Germany shows, the following measures are necessary for the successful post-war reconstruction of Ukraine:

- 1) support and development of the existing research base in order to activate scientific, scientific, technical and innovative activities together with ensuring the transfer of technology from the inventor to the manufacturer;

- 2) state stimulation of innovative activity of corporations, creation of motivation for financial support of small and medium-sized innovative businesses (startups, venture enterprises, etc.), implementation of a policy of professional development of employees, creation of their own research laboratories and development on this basis of high-tech production networks that can quickly respond to changes in global market conditions [4, p.43].

In Ukraine, back in 2022, immediately after the large-scale invasion of Russia, the Government and the Office of the President launched a plan for the restoration of Ukraine, based on 5 basic principles:

1. Immediate start and gradual development: the Plan aims to accelerate sustainable economic growth.

2. Building fair prosperity: the goal is for Ukraine to become a strong European country that attracts foreign investment.

3. EU integration: the Plan promotes rapprochement with the European Union.

4. Restoration of better than it has been on a national and regional scale: focused on improving the lives of citizens and developing regions.

5. Stimulation of private investment: the Plan helps attract capital for the project implementation [5].

The Plan includes national programs such as:

- Strengthening institutional capacity
- Digital State
- Strengthening defense and security
- Striving for EU integration
- Restoring a clean and protected environment
- Energy independence and a green course
- And many others [5].

Conclusion. The Country Recovery Plan is an important step for Ukraine’s recovery after the war and the implementation of the country’s strategic goals, but only if the global experience of recovering post-war economies is used in this case - its creative development and adaptation to Ukrainian realities and in conditions of proper planning, which includes such important links as defining goals, choosing strategies and determining actions that are required to achieve these goals with the limited (in our exceptional case) resources available to donor organizations. It is worth noting that the population itself can be a fairly powerful investor in the reconstruction of the country through the mechanism of internal borrowing, but this is possible in a democracy only with proper trust in the current government.

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